

TYPOLOGY OF THE GRAMMATICAL CATEGORY OF MOOD IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

Ismailova Muazzam Uroyimjonovna

Master's degree, teacher at Uychi school #3

ismoilova.muazzam@mail.ru

Abstract: This thesis discusses the comparison of verb tenses in Uzbek and English languages and the elimination of difficulties encountered in teaching them.

Key words: typology, comparison, verb mood, category

INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILIDA FE'L MAYLI GRAMMATIK KATEGORIYASI TIPOLOGIYASI

Ismoilova Muazzam Uroyimjonovna

Magistratura, Uychi №3 maktabda o'qituvchi

ismoilova.muazzam@mail.ru

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezisdagi o'zbek va ingliz tillarida fe'l mayllarini solishtirish va ularni o'rgatishda duch keladigan qiyinchiliklarni bartaraf etish haqida so'z yuritiladi.

Tayanch so'zlar: tipologiya, qiyoslash, fe'l mayli, kategoriya

ТИПОЛОГИЯ ГРАММАТИЧЕСКОЙ КАТЕГОРИИ НАКЛОНЕНИЯ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

Исмоилова Муаззам Уройимжоновна

Магистр, учитель Уйчиской школы №3

ismoilova.muazzam@mail.ru

Аннотация: В данной тезисе рассматривается сравнение времен глаголов в узбекском и английском языках и устранение трудностей, возникающих при их обучении.

Ключевые слова: типология, сравнение, наклонение глагола, категория.

The object of this study is to compare verb moods in Uzbek and English and to overcome the difficulties encountered in teaching them. The subject of the research is the comparison of verb declensions in Uzbek and English. The goal of the research is to improve interactive technologies for overcoming difficulties encountered in teaching verb tenses. In the course of research, the practical, educational, educational and developmental potential of English language classes has been clarified, the principles of teaching inclinations have been improved, and the improvement of integrative technologies that help to develop the potential of students to understand and apply verb inclinations in English classes is envisaged.

In this case, the object field of the study can be classified by the steps such as **Comparative Typology as a branch of General Linguistics** (Historical background of typological investigations, Comparative Typology: subject matter, types, tasks, approaches and classifications), **Typology of the grammatical category of mood of English and Uzbek languages** (Typology of the grammatical category of mood of English language Typology of the grammatical category of mood of Uzbek language), **Teaching and denoting of the grammatical category of mood in English and Uzbek languages** (Recommendations for overcoming difficulties in teaching the grammatical category of mood, Organization of experiment and its results).